

Report on Intellectual Outputs of the project GREEN ENERGY SKILLS FOR YOUTH

ERASMUS+

THE CENTRE FOR EUROPEAN UNION EDUCATION AND YOUTH
PROGRAMMES (TURKISH NATIONAL AGENCY)

Cooperation for innovation and the exchange of good practices

Strategic Partnerships

Strategic Partnerships for youth

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GREEN ENERGY SKILLS FOR YOUTH (GREEN4U)
Project Report on the Intellectual of the Project

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www.green4uproject.eu

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Contents

1 Acknowledgement	2
2 Introduction	4
3 Intellectual Outputs	5
Glossary on Green Energy	5
Online Learning Management System	7
Infographics	8
Serious Games	11
GAME1: Build your own wind power plant	11
GAME2: Define Needed Energy for Your Home Town (Dilema: Green or Not Green?)	18
GAME3: Green Memory	22
GAME4: EcoLogica Quiz	25
GAME5: Green Warrior	28
GAME6: Green Candy Crush	33
GAME7: Green Warrior - Candy Crush Game Special Waste Management Edition	37
After The Games	42
Postface	54
Data Privacy, Gaming and Green For Youth Games	55
Annex	56
3rd International Scientific Conference on Philosophy of Mind and Cognitive Modelling in Education	56
International Conference on Sustainable Energy and Energy Calculations . .	67

Introduction

Green Energy Skills for Youth (GREEN4U) provides a number of interactive digital tools for youth aged 13-25 years old. Through these tools the beneficiaries of the project meet the learning demands in the nature, ecosystem, green energy, pollution, carbon footprint, energy and waste management. The project supply beneficiaries with a number of serious games¹ devoted to the green energy topics. These games are specially produced after a wide investigation of the backgrounds, the interests and the lack of the knowledge of the youth interviewed in the first six months of the project. We have conducted more than 3000 young people and asked them numerous questions². After analyzing the answers we have concluded that young generation is actualy in need of material through which they can get information and awarenes on green energy topics. The material is specially of high interest when it is digital, namely, available on our mobile devices, laptops, mobile phones, tablets³.

In this report, which can be read also as a user's manual on the intellectual outputs of the project, we describe the serious games of the project, we instruct the usage of the outputs. However, the outputs of the project may have a wide range of different usages by any beneficiary. In the project we have produced seven serious games on green energy topics. In the rest of the report we give the details of the seven games and instruct the usages. Besides the games, we give a glossary on green energy topics in our web site and also a number of presentation file in our training module of the project.

In the annexes we present our papers out of the project, which demonstrate the results and findings of the project.

¹A serious game or applied game is a game designed for a primary purpose other than pure entertainment. The "serious" adjective is generally prepended to refer to video games used by industries like defense, education, scientific exploration, health care, emergency management, city planning, engineering, and politics.

²The results of the survey has been published and can be reached at the Annex 1.

³The results of the project has been published and can be reached at the Annex 2

Intellectual Outputs

In the project we have produced seven serious games on green energy topics. In the rest of the report we give the details of the seven games and instruct the usages. Besides the games, we give a glossary on green energy topics in our web site and also a number of presentation file in our training module of the project.

Glossary on Green Energy

In our web site one find find a glossary on green energy subject, through which he/she can get a first impression on energy topics. The web site address is

<http://green4uproject.eu/glossary/>

Green Energy? We got answers!

Climate Change

A change in global or regional climate patterns, in particular a change apparent from the mid to late 20th century onwards and attributed largely to the increased levels of atmospheric carbon dioxide produced by the use of fossil fuels.

Waste Management

Waste management or Waste disposal is all the activities and actions required to manage waste from its inception to its final disposal. This includes amongst other things collection, transport, treatment and disposal of waste together with monitoring and regulation.

Practice

- Visit the web site and click on the items. Read the explanation and see the pictures.

Ecosystem	
Energy Conservation	
Pollution	
Waste Management	
Recycling	
Greenhouse Gases	
Renewable Energy	
Wind Turbine	
Geothermal Energy	
Thermal Solar Panel	
Tidal Power	

Online Learning Management System

For our project we have dedicated a well known Learning Management System (LMS) on green energy topics. Beneficiaris, trainers, teacher and so on are invited to get registered on the system and use the system and get the material inside. The web address of the system is

<http://training.green4uproject.eu/>

Currently there are six courses available:

1. Renewable Energy,
2. Pollution,
3. Carbon footprint,
4. Ecosystem,
5. Recycling,
6. Climate Change.

The default user name enrolled to the courses is:

username = green4u

password = Green4U\$

Practice

- Visit the web site and log the system in,
- Click Courses,
- Select the topic,
- Reach the learning material available,
- Read and study the material.

The screenshot shows a Moodle course page for 'RENEWABLE ENERGY'. The breadcrumb trail is 'Home > My courses > renewableenergy'. A navigation menu on the left lists 'Home', 'Dashboard', 'Site pages', 'My courses', and sub-items for 'renewableenergy', 'ecosystem', 'recycling', 'pollution', 'ClimateChange', and 'CARBONFOOTPRINT'. On the right, there are 'Announcements' for 'renewable energy' with dates: '28 July - 3 August', '4 August - 10 August', and '11 August - 17 August'.

The banner features logos for TÜRKİYE ULUSAL AJANSI (TURKISH NATIONAL AGENCY), TÜRK-ALMAN ÜNİVERSİTESİ (TURKISH-GERMAN UNIVERSITY), and ZETA zentralweb /> KIBLA smart web solutions. The text reads: 'GREEN ENERGY SKILLS FOR YOUTH ERASMUS+' and 'PROJECT NUMBER: 2016-2-TR01-KA205-03600'.

The infographic is split into two sections. The top section, 'What is Recycling?', features a cartoon character thinking. The bottom section, 'What's Environmental Pollution?', shows a polluted river with text: 'Environmental pollution in any an undesirable change in physical, chemical, or biological characteristics of any component of the environment'.

The infographic is titled 'RENEWABLE ENERGY' and defines 'Renewable Energy Resource' as 'An essentially inexhaustible energy resource on a human time scale.' It includes images of solar panels and wind turbines. The bottom section, 'Climate change', defines it as 'Weather patterns, glaciers, sea level rise...' and notes 'Climate change is a significant change in weather patterns. When you peck in the perspective of a longer period of time you find it has happened many times before.' with a '100 000 years' scale.

The infographic is titled 'What is an ecosystem' and defines it as 'An ecosystem is a grouping of organisms that interact with each other and their environment in such a way as to preserve the grouping.' It also states 'There is a great variety of ecosystems in existence, all of them are characterized by general structural and functional attributes.' The bottom section, 'Carbon Footprint', shows a footprint with 'CO2' and lists objectives: 'To understand the term carbon footprint.', 'To be able to evaluate information and work independently.', and 'To be able to create your carbon footprint, and explain'.

Infographics

We have produced two infographics on green energy subjects. One is about recycling the other is about pollution.

What Is Carbon Footprint

A carbon footprint is the measure of the impact our activities have on the environment, and in particular climate change.

Carbon Footprint is about the amount of carbon dioxide produced in our day-to-day lives and released into the atmosphere through burning fossil fuels for electricity, heating and transportation etc.

Cooking

Driving a car

Flying

Celebrating

Working

Heating a house

For instance, CO₂ and other emissions are caused when

It really is surprising how much CO₂ emissions we produce in everyday life.

POLLUTION!

Contaminants enter to natural environment and causes pollution; which is anything that makes our planet dirty and unhealthy.

Things as simple as light, sound and temperature can be considered pollutants!

Since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution, earth has been affected by environmental pollution.

TÜRK-ALMAN ÜNİVERSİTESİ
TÜRKİSCH-DEUTSCHE UNIVERSITÄT

University of Istanbul
Faculty of Natural Sciences
and Mathematics

KIBLA

zentralweb />
smart web solutions

ZETA

Air, water and land are all affected by pollution and this threatens human health.

Air Pollution

Harmful chemicals, particulate matter, aerosols, toxic and hazardous gases, and organic material enters the atmosphere, and causes air pollution. Most air pollution results from automobile and industrial exhausts which cause severe air quality degradation and play an important role in increasing air pollution.

Land Pollution

Land can become polluted by household garbage and by industrial waste. When a pollutant gets introduced in the lithosphere, it directly affects the environment, causing land pollution which impacts the entire food chain. This is the most hazardous of all types of pollution.

Water Pollution

Harmful chemicals, gases, and waste products enter water bodies, and lead to contamination of water causing water pollution. Water pollution happens when harmful chemicals, gases dangerous foreign substances like waste products are introduced to water.

STOPPING POLLUTION STARTS

WITH YOU!

Serious Games

The seven serious games of the project are available at

<http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/>

GAME1: Build your own wind power plant

Description of the game and learning objectives

The students will learn the theory of wind turbines. The instructor may additionally give some theoretical background and explain the mechanism of producing electricity by wind turbines. Furthermore the students may pay attention the execution of wind turbines.

The students will work individually. They will analyse how much energy spent by their family and how big wind turbine he/she will need. He/she will analyse the wind condition in their area, according to this date student will simulate and calculate the needed energy. Then he/she can compare data with other students and analyse results, to found the best solution.

Curriculum covered (learning scenarios)

Selection of the specific cognitive competencies which the game covers. Problem solving, communication competences, social competences (Team working, multiplaying, social interaction).

Availability

The game can be played online on any digital platform by visiting the web site

<http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ Click "Hey! Would you like to build your wind farm online?".

Game structure

1. Analyse needs for energy
2. Simulation of wind energy production
3. Putting the question
4. Solve theproblem

5. Evaluate (analyze) the results
6. Explain deviation
7. Improve the resolution/optimization

Distinctive features

Supported platforms: Windows, Linux and MacOS; Can be played on Android and OSX.

3D environment: no

Interactions: yes

Automatization: no Game map: yes

Text-to-speech: no

Language support: All

Control mechanism (buttons): Mouse, keyboard, touch screen

Online/offline use: Online/online use

Characters and environment

Playable characters

Non-playable characters: yes

Style

Structure

Content customisation: yes

Graphics quality: 2D

Game narrative

Description of the game narrative

Audio playback: no

Reward mechanism

Feedback of the game: yes

Possible reward to be included: yes (printing rewards on 3D printer)

How to learn by playing

Background

Before letting the students play the game, the students can be given by the following information:

Production of Wind Power

Wind is produced in the earth's atmosphere due to difference in earth temperatures locally or on a regional and global scale. When warm becomes heated it rises leaving the place with low air pressure; air from cooler regions with higher pressures of air moves in to equalize air pressure.

Wind mills and turbines take advantage of the kinetic energy or "motion energy" that moves air or wind from one place to another and converts it to electricity. Wind turbines are erected in windy places, so the wind can move the blades of turbines. These blades rotate a motor, and gears increase the rotations enough to produce electricity. Different designs of turbines are suitable for varying conditions.

Wind Efficiency and Wind Capacity Factor

Wind efficiency is the amount of kinetic energy in the wind that is converted to mechanical energy and electricity. Laws of physics described by Betz Limit says the maximum theoretical limit is 59.6%. The wind requires the rest of the energy to blow past the blades. This is in fact good. If a turbine trapped 100% of energy wind would stop blowing and the blades of a turbine cannot turn to produce electricity.

It is, however, not possible for any machine, at present to convert all of the trapped 59.6% of kinetic energy from wind to electricity. There are limits due to the way generators are made and engineered, which further decrease the amount of energy that is finally converted to power. The average at present is 35-45%, as noted above. The maximum at peak performance could reach 50% according to Wind Watch.

Energy efficiency does not vary as much as wind capacity factor does which is dependant to a great extent on location and weather conditions.

Wind Capacity Factor

The wind capacity factor is the amount of energy produced by a generator as against what it could produce if it functioned all the time at peak capacity, according to Green Tech Media. Wind capacity factor tends to vary from place to place and at different times of the year, even with the same turbines, since it depends on the speed of wind, its density and swept area that depends on the size of the generator. Wind capacity factor can be optimised by

choosing places where ideal wind conditions prevail the whole or greater part of the year. So it is important to consider wind capacity factor and the conditions influencing it to maximise power output.

- Wind speed below 30 miles per hour produces little energy according to Wind Watch. Even small increases in speed can translate into substantial increase in power. Electricity generated is the cube of the wind speed.
- Air density is more in cooler regions and at sea level than in mountains. So the ideal places with high wind density are seas with colder temperatures. This is one reason for the large scale expansion in off-shore wind generation.
- Larger and taller turbines can take advantage of more wind higher above the ground and by the increased span of their blades. Economic considerations therefore become important here.

The capacity factor is constantly being increased with improved technology. Wind turbines built in 2014 reached a capacity factor of 41.2% as compared to 31.2% for turbines built between 2004-2011, according to Green Tech Media. However, the capacity factor of wind is affected not only by technology, but also wind availability itself.

Practice

The screenshot shows a web browser window with the URL `green-games.eu/wind/`. The page features a language selection bar with buttons for SLO, ENG (selected), GER, and TUR. Below this is a text box stating: "Efficiency calculation of a windshield with a horizontal axis. We assume that the shape and number of the blades are optimal. The air temperature is 15°C." The main interface consists of three sliders: "Choose wind speed [m/s]" set to 1, "Please choose blade size [m]" set to 1, and "Please choose rated output power [MW]" set to 0.1. At the bottom, two results are displayed: "Power of the wind" as 0.0000192419999999999997 MW and "Wind turbine efficiency" as 51968.9610. The background of the application is a photograph of a wind farm at sunset.

The game is advised to be played in a classroom. Each student or each group will play the game and present their optimal solution to their energy demand problem.

- Visit <http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ Click "Hey! Would you like to build your wind farm online?",
- Choose a suitable language,
- By tuning the options fill the Table 3.1 in for 10 different cases.

Table 3.1: Your wind turbine

Wind Speed (m/s)	Blade Size (m)	Output Power (MW)	Power Of Wind (MW)	Efficiency

- Plot Wind Speed versus Efficiency,
- Plot Blade Size versus Efficiency,

- Discuss "Why cannot we have very small and very long blades?",
- Discuss "Why cannot we have many blades?",
- Discuss "Why do not we like very speedy wind?",
- Get feedbacks from the students and ask some "crazy" ideas.

GAME2: Define Needed Energy for Your Home Town (Dilema: Green or Not Green?)

Description of the game and learning objectives

The students will learn fundamentals of energy sources. Furthermore they will pay attention to carbon footprint and pollution.

Description of the learning context into which it will be used.

(Teambuilding, establish good working relationships and environment.

Problem solving, Communication with and without feedback, following the instruction, putting the question

Curriculum covered (learning scenarios)

Teamworking, Problem solving, communication competences, social competences (Team working, multiplaying, social interaction).

Availability

The game can be played online on any digital platform by visiting the web site

<http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ Click "Hey! Would you like to build your green city online?"

Game structure

1. Known the players, introduces, select the individual role in the team
2. Teambuilding
3. Follow the instruction
4. Establishing working relationship
5. Negotiation, understanding goals of the team
6. Solve the problem
7. Evaluate (analyze) the results
8. Explain deviation
9. Improve the solution/optimization

Distinctive features

Supported platforms: Windows, Linux and MacOS; Can be played on Android and OSX.

3D environment: no

Interactions: yes

Automatization: no

Game map: yes

Text-to-speech: no

Language support: All

Control mechanism (buttons): Mouse, keyboard, touch screen

Online/offline use: Online/online use

Characters and environment

Playable characters

Non-playable characters: yes

Style

Structure

Content customisation: yes

Graphics quality: 2D

Game narrative

Description of the game narrative

Audio playback: no

Reward mechanism

Feedback of the game: yes

Possible reward to be included: yes (printing rewards on 3D printer)

How to learn by playing

Practice

The game is advised to be played in a classroom. Each student or each group will play the game and present their optimal solution to their energy demand problem.

- Visit <http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ Click "Hey! Would you like to build your green city online?"
- Choose a suitable language,
- Choose any workshop,
- Give your name and grade,
- Select "Day" or "Night",
- Ask the students to set a specific number of inhabitants, every student set the same set of inhabitants,
- Fill Table 3.2 in for 10 different cases.

GAME3: Green Memory

Description of the game and learning objectives

The students will play a memory game of three different levels. The game is of green energy concepts.

Curriculum covered (learning scenarios)

Time-based playing, more awareness on green energy.

Availability

The game can be played online on any digital platform by visiting the web site

<http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ "Hey! Would you like to play our memory game online?"

Furthermore the application can be downloaded on your mobile phone and installed (Please allow your phone so that third-party softwares can be installed).

While playing games is a great leisure activity that people of all ages can enjoy, games can also be used for learning and educational experiences. Some games have been found to improve cognitive functions like memory and reasoning. Other games have the potential to reverse aging related brain function problems such as short term memory loss.

Game structure

1. have pleasure,
2. enhance your brain functions,
3. exercise your brain on green energy,
4. stimulate your minds of green energy,
5. enhance visual discrimination on green energy,
6. enhance power of recognition on green energy,
7. increase short memory on green energy,
8. improve creativity on green energy,
9. have more foresight on green energy,

10. improve vocabulary on green energy.

Distinctive features

Supported platforms: Can be played on Android and OSX.

Control mechanism (buttons): Mouse, keyboard, touch screen

Online/offline use: Online/online use

Characters and environment

Playable characters

Non-playable characters: yes

Style

Structure

Content customisation: yes

Graphics quality: 2D

Game narrative

Description of the game: memorial

Audio playback: yes

Reward mechanism

Feedback of the game: yes

How to learn by playing

Practice

- Start the game playing online or installing on your phone,
- Choose the level,
- Try to match the green energy symbols in the given time,
- Ask yourself which new green energy topics you have met,
- Ask yourself which other green energy energy topics could be included.

GAME4: EcoLogica Quiz

Description of the game and learning objectives

The students will play a quiz game of three green energy topic. The game is of green energy concepts. The topics included are:

- Carbon Footprint,
- Climate Change,
- Energy & Conversion,
- Pollution,
- Renewable Energy,
- Waste Management.

Curriculum covered (learning scenarios)

Time-based playing, more awareness on green energy.

Availability

The game can be played online on any digital platform by visiting the web site

<http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ "Hey! Would you like to play our quiz game?"

Furthermore the application can be downloaded on your mobile phone and installed (Please allow your phone so that third-party softwares can be installed).

A quiz is a game which can also be called a mind sport wherein the players, either as individuals or in teams attempt to answer questions posed to them correctly, in order to win a prize.

Game structure

1. Assess Knowledge on green energy,
2. Motivate Learners on green energy,
3. Engage Learners on green energy,
4. Improve Knowledge Retention and Transfer.

Distinctive features

Supported platforms: Can be played on Android and OSX.

Control mechanism (buttons): Mouse, keyboard, touch screen

Online/offline use: Online/online use

Characters and environment

Playable characters

Non-playable characters: yes

Style

Structure

Content customisation: yes

Graphics quality: 2D

Game narrative

Description of the game: memorial

Audio playback: yes

Reward mechanism

Feedback of the game: yes

How to learn by playing

Practice

- Download the apk file,
- Install it on your mobile phone,
- Choose your language,
- Choose category,
- Answer the multiple choice questions in a required time,
- Apply online source for missing knowledge,
- Improve your score.

GAME5: Green Warrior

Description of the game and learning objectives

Green Warrior is a platform game made with Unity3D (real-time tools offer incredible possibilities for game developers, and creators across industries and applications in 2D, 3D, VR, and AR). The engine can be used to create both three-dimensional and two-dimensional games as well as simulations for its many platforms especially for mobile games. The platform games, or platformer, is a video game genre and subgenre of action game for the kids. In a platformer the player controls a character or avatar to jump between suspended platforms and avoid obstacles. Environments often feature uneven terrain requiring jumping and climbing in order to traverse them. These types of games are suitable for the Generation Z kids. Since they are multitaskers with short attention spans, similar to their older Gen Y siblings, so will often have multiple screens surrounding them. The generation has an always-on, on-demand mentality they watch what they want, when they want it. Because they are constantly switching from screen to screen, and have an attention span (or tolerance) of just eight seconds, its easy for them to give messages or train with games. If they dont enjoy watching, they will simply move onto something they do like. Gen Z also favours shorter content, preferring videos less than 20 seconds long. To catch their gaze, traditional entertainment providers may need to provide extra content of varied lengths and delivery methods, with integrated. Green Warrior game is created according to the above requirements.

Curriculum covered (learning scenarios)

Auditory Short-term Memory: The ability to remember game over a brief period of time

Contextual Memory: The conscious recall of the Green4U subjects source and circumstances of a specific memory icons

Divided Attention: The ability to execute more than one action at a time, while paying attention to a few channels of information both as the environment, messages, icons, wind, physics of the game

Focus: The ability to focus attention on a single enemy, task to jump between flying islands etc

Hand-eye Coordination: The level of sensitivity with which the hand and eye are synchronized in order to succeed and play

Planning: The ability to "think ahead", to mentally anticipate the correct way to execute a task especially with the moving objects, enemies and jumping between different speed

objects

Recognition: The ability to retrieve information from the past and to recognize certain events, places or other information like stopping the black smoke and the physical phenomenon on the game

Response Time: The ability to perceive and process a simple stimulus and respond to it to succeed in gameplay

Spatial Perception: The ability to evaluate how things are arranged in space, and investigate their relations in the game environment.

Visual Perception: The ability to interpret information from the effects of visible light reaching the eye in the gameplay

Visual Scanning: The ability to actively find relevant information in our surroundings quickly and efficiently in the gameplay like moving objects in the environment

Estimation: The ability to estimate an object's future location based on its current speed and distance of the enemies

Width of Field of View: Corresponds to amount of information we receive from around when looking straight ahead.

Availability

The game can be played online on any digital platform by visiting the web site

<http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ "Hey! Would you like to play our action game?"

Furthermore the application can be downloaded on your mobile phone and installed (Please allow your phone so that third-party softwares can be installed).

Game structure

Green Warrior Game has four levels,

1. Level 1 :Carbon Footprint
2. Level 2 :Climate Change Ecosystem
3. Level 3: Waste Management
4. Level 4: Energy Conversion

Each level has 3 stages, Easy for all players and can be easily completed, so all the kids can play and see what is going on, medium and hard for them to keep playing and getting more contact with the subjects and ideas of Green4U Project.

Distinctive features

Supported platforms: All platforms can be compiled with unity, but Adroid APK and Apple Store formats generated

3D environment: Unity 3D

Language support: Gameplay

Control mechanism (buttons): Touch enabled

For the game platform

- 2D Physics Platformer system
- Walk, Run, Jump, Double Jump , Wall Jump, Shoot, Walk on slopes...
- 2D Water / Swimming
- Zoom in + Zoom Out function
- Moving Platforms
- Keyboard, Mobile & Gamepad Controls
- Slope Handling
- Gamepad vibration (Windows Only)
- Wall Jump
- Background and foreground Parallax
- Animated Checkpoints System
- Items pick up System
- AI in Enemies

- Health System
- Main Menu and Level Selection
- Original outlined art
- Smooth animations
- Awesome particle effects
- Weapons System
- Full Platformer Gui System

Characters and environment

Playable characters:

The Green Warrior (Aka Archer) According to the survey results and focus group talks kids wants to play with the strong characters but also since they are kids they dont want to be a powerful alien, old aged paladin or white breasted wizard, instead they want to be powerful humanoid children character. Also even the game is a platformer game with some weapons and enemies the main concept should be the Green4U Project. According to those requirements, Archer Character is evolved for the game. The following main capabilities of the character is defined and created as 2D and 3D models with animations.

Non-playable characters: The environmental pollutant, dirty wastes (Aka Enemies) created according to the idea of this is an educational game.

Style

SGraphics quality : HD Graphics and Unity Quality Optimization used

Game narrative

Green Warrior (aka Archer) is fighting for the environmental pollutant enemies and wastes during the game, sometimes by avoiding them or sometimes closing a Black Fossil Fuel Smoke from a waste discharge source.

Every level he collects some reward icons related with the Green4U Subjects. Also game environment and subtitles gives messages and mottos.

Reward mechanism

Feedback of the game : Scoring and getting points in each level to be awarded for the next level with more difficulties Possible reward to be included : Special icons for random rewards such a double points

How to learn by playing

Practice

- Download the apk file,
- Install it on your mobile phone,
- Play and enjoy the game.
- Discuss what green energy topics are met,
- Work in a classroom. After playing the game, ask the students, individual or small groups, draw a poster on green energy topics. Let them present their work. Observe the tendency of topics included in the posters.

GAME6: Green Candy Crush

Description of the game and learning objectives

Green Candy Crush is a puzzle game made with Unity3D (real-time tools offer incredible possibilities for game developers, and creators across industries and applications in 2D, 3D, VR, and AR). The engine can be used to create both three-dimensional and two-dimensional games as well as simulations for its many platforms especially for mobile games. In the original game, players complete levels by swapping colored pieces of cand on a game board to make a match of three or more of the same color, eliminating those candies from the board and replacing them with new ones, which could potentially create further matches. Matches of four or more candies create unique candies that act as power-ups with larger board-clearing abilities. Boards have various goals that must be completed within a fixed number of moves or limited amount of time, such as a certain score or collecting a specific number of a type of candy. King first released Candy Crush Saga on Facebook in April of 2012, and it became a quick success. Within a year of its launch, it had reached 500 million phone downloads. The numbers continued to grow. Currently, games within the Candy Crush franchise (which include Candy Crush Soda Saga and Candy Crush Jelly Saga) have been downloaded a grand total of 2.73 billion times. It has 70 million Facebook fans, and has been downloaded on all seven continents. And the app's not just sitting unused on people's phone's, either: 1.1 trillion rounds of the game have been played around the world to date. Many people play daily, with a total of 115,000 kilometers (71,458 miles) swiped by fingers every single day which, the makers point out, is the equivalent of running a collective 2725 marathons. The idea is Everybody wants to play games with Candy Crush Style According to the surveys and focus groups with kids they also like to play and if possible, they want to learn some subjects while they are playing. So as the Green4U Project the Candy Icons replaced with the icons related with Green4U project icons. Green Warrior game is created according to the above requirements and the earning objectives are creating a photographic memory of the subjects in each main focus area.

Curriculum covered (learning scenarios)

Auditory Short-term Memory: The ability to remember game over a brief period of time

Contextual Memory: The conscious recall of the Green4U subjects source and circumstances of a specific memory icons

Divided Attention: The ability to execute more than one action at a time, while paying attention to a few channels of information both as the environment, messages, icons, wind,

physics of the game

Focus: The ability to focus attention on a single enemy, task to jump between flying islands etc

Hand-eye Coordination: The level of sensitivity with which the hand and eye are synchronized in order to succeed and play

Planning: The ability to "think ahead", to mentally anticipate the correct way to execute a task especially with the moving objects, enemies and jumping between different speed objects

Recognition: The ability to retrieve information from the past and to recognize certain events, places or other information like stopping the black smoke and the physical phenomenon on the game

Response Time: The ability to perceive and process a simple stimulus and respond to it to succeed in gameplay

Spatial Perception: The ability to evaluate how things are arranged in space, and investigate their relations in the game environment.

Visual Perception: The ability to interpret information from the effects of visible light reaching the eye in the gameplay

Visual Scanning: The ability to actively find relevant information in our surroundings quickly and efficiently in the gameplay like moving objects in the environment

Estimation: The ability to estimate an object's future location based on its current speed and distance of the enemies

Width of Field of View: Corresponds to amount of information we receive from around when looking straight ahead.

Availability

The game can be played online on any digital platform by visiting the web site

<http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ "Hey! Would you like to play our management game?"

Furthermore the application can be downloaded on your mobile phone and installed (Please allow your phone so that third-party softwares can be installed).

Game structure

This game is devoted to Waste Management.

Distinctive features

Supported platforms: All platforms can be compiled with unity, but Adroid APK and Apple Store formats generated

3D environment: Unity 3D

Language support: Gameplay

Control mechanism (buttons): Touch enabled

For the game platform

- 2D Physics Platformer system

Characters and environment

Playable characters:

The Green Warrior (Aka Archer) According to the survey results and focus group talks kids wants to play with the strong characters but also since they are kids they dont want to be a powerful alien, old aged paladin or white breaded wizard, instead they want to be powerful humanoid children character. Also even the game is a platformer game with some weapons and enemies the main concept should be the Green4U Project. According to those requirements, Archer Character is evolved for the game. The following main capabilities of the character is defined and created as 2D and 3D models with animations.

Non-playable characters: The environmental pollutant, dirty wastes (Aka Enemies) created according to the idea of this is an educational game.

Style

SGraphics quality : HD Graphics and Unity Quality Optimization used

Game narrative

Play like the classical candy crush game with Green4U Environment

Reward mechanism

Feedback of the game : Scoring and getting points in each level to be awarded for the next level with more difficulties Possible reward to be included : Special icons for random rewards such a double points

How to learn by playing

Practice

- Download the apk file,
- Install it on your mobile phone,
- Play and enjoy the game.
- Discuss what green energy topics are met.
- Work in a classroom. After playing the game, ask the students, individual or small groups, draw a poster on green energy topics. Let them present their work. Observe the tendency of topics included in the posters.

GAME7: Green Warrior - Candy Crush Game Special Waste Management Edition

Description of the game and learning objectives

This is the special version of Green Warrior with Waste Management Topic.

Curriculum covered (learning scenarios)

Auditory Short-term Memory: The ability to remember game over a brief period of time

Contextual Memory: The conscious recall of the Green4U subjects source and circumstances of a specific memory icons

Divided Attention: The ability to execute more than one action at a time, while paying attention to a few channels of information both as the environment, messages, icons, wind, physics of the game

Focus: The ability to focus attention on a single enemy, task to jump between flying islands etc

Hand-eye Coordination: The level of sensitivity with which the hand and eye are synchronized in order to succeed and play

Planning: The ability to "think ahead", to mentally anticipate the correct way to execute a task especially with the moving objects, enemies and jumping between different speed objects

Recognition: The ability to retrieve information from the past and to recognize certain events, places or other information like stopping the black smoke and the physical phenomenon on the game

Response Time: The ability to perceive and process a simple stimulus and respond to it to succeed in gameplay

Spatial Perception: The ability to evaluate how things are arranged in space, and investigate their relations in the game environment.

Visual Perception: The ability to interpret information from the effects of visible light reaching the eye in the gameplay

Visual Scanning: The ability to actively find relevant information in our surroundings quickly and efficiently in the gameplay like moving objects in the environment

Estimation: The ability to estimate an object's future location based on its current speed and distance of the enemies

Width of Field of View: Corresponds to amount of information we receive from around

when looking straight ahead.

Availability

The game can be played online on any digital platform by visiting the web site

<http://green4uproject.eu/games4youth/> ⇒ "Hey! Would you like to play our crush game?".

Furthermore the application can be downloaded on your mobile phone and installed (Please allow your phone so that third-party softwares can be installed).

Game structure

Green Candy Crush Game has four levels,

1. Level 1 :Carbon Footprint
2. Level 2 :Climate Change Ecosystem
3. Level 3: Waste Management
4. Level 4: Energy Conversion

All levels have some targets to collect as the rewards

Distinctive features

Supported platforms: All platforms can be compiled with unity, but Adroid APK and Apple Store formats generated

3D environment: Unity 3D

Language support: Gameplay

Control mechanism (buttons): Touch enabled

For the game platform

- 2D Physics Platformer system

Characters and environment

Playable characters:

The Green Warrior (Aka Archer) According to the survey results and focus group talks kids wants to play with the strong characters but also since they are kids they dont want to be a powerful alien, old aged paladin or white breaded wizard, instead they want to be powerful humanoid children character. Also even the game is a platformer game with some weapons and enemies the main concept should be the Green4U Project. According to those requirements, Archer Character is evolved for the game. The following main capabilities of the character is defined and created as 2D and 3D models with animations.

Non-playable characters: The environmental pollutant, dirty wastes (Aka Enemies) created according to the idea of this is an educational game.

- Install it on your mobile phone,
- Play and enjoy the game.
- Discuss what green energy topics are met.
- Work in a classroom. After playing the game, ask the students, individual or small groups, draw a poster on green energy topics. Let them present their work. Observe the tendency of topics included in the posters.

After The Games

After exercising with the games of the projects, the students are encouraged to conduct a kind of survey questions and get measured in green energy topics. The prepared survey questions are following. The instructor may like to modify the survey.

Gamings' Measurement Questions, Answers' Key and Optical Sheet

Here is a set of questions on green energy topics prepared for young people aged 13-25. Answers' key is also given, an optical sheet as well.

Name:
Date:
Surname:
Signature:

Green 4

2016-2-TR01-KA205-036001

SURVEY TO MEASURE GREEN ENERGY AWARENESS

- 1) Reusing or recycling old items instead of buying new ones helps shrink your carbon footprint by...
 - A) Eliminating the need for new packaging to be created
 - B) Cutting out the CO₂ released when transporting new products to the store
 - C) Making sure you don't buy more than you need
 - D) All of the above
 - E) None of the above
- 2) Rubber or plastic shoes usually have a higher carbon footprint than canvas ones because...
 - A) They have bigger soles
 - B) They're made of petroleum (oil-based) products, which are often processed in big factories
 - C) Plastic comes from the *Plasticus plantae* plant, which needs to be watered every hour to survive
 - D) It is hard to walk with them, so you need a car for going to other places
 - E) All of the above
- 3) Which of these fabrics usually has a lower carbon footprint? (Hint: it can be organic and is biodegradable!)
 - A) Nylon
 - B) Polyester
 - C) Cotton
 - D) Fleece
 - E) Acrylic
- 4) Where's the best place to shop to keep your carbon footprint small?

- A) A farmer's market you can walk to, just around the corner
 - B) The outlet store an hour's drive away (you can't beat the deals on a 10 pack of peanut butter!)
 - C) The grocery store by your best friend's house in the next town over – you guys like to do everything together!
 - D) A shopping mall in the middle of the town
 - E) Going to another city using a very cheap plane ticket
- 5) Old-school incandescent lightbulbs have a higher carbon footprint than new fluorescent ones because...
- A) They use less energy
 - B) They have to be replaced more often
 - C) They're the only type of lightbulb used in factories
 - D) They emit more light
 - E) They also heat their surroundings
- 6) Which of these impacts may result from climate change by 2100?
- A) Global temperatures will rise by 2.5 to 10 degrees, and sea levels will rise by 1 to 4 feet.
 - B) Pests and mosquito-borne diseases will spread to new areas.
 - C) Hurricanes and rainstorms will become more extreme.
 - D) All of the above
 - E) None of the above
- 7) Which of the following activities contributes the most to carbon emissions globally?
- A) Agriculture
 - B) Transport
 - C) Forestry
 - D) Energy supply
 - E) Commercial & residential
- 8) Which of these countries has the highest per capita carbon dioxide emissions?
- A) United States
 - B) Australia
 - C) Saudi Arabia
 - D) China
 - E) Japan

- 9) Which of these countries emits the most carbon dioxide?
- A) China
 - B) USA
 - C) UK
 - D) Russia
 - E) Japan
- 10) How much has our planet warmed already, on average?
- A) 0.5 degrees Celsius
 - B) 2.0 degrees Celsius
 - C) 1.5 degrees Celsius
 - D) 1.0 degrees Celsius
 - E) 3 degrees
- 11) The lowest level of environmental community that includes living and nonliving together is called
- A) Biome
 - B) Ecosystem
 - C) Community
 - D) Biosphere
 - E) Population
- 12) Which of the following can be the function of an organism in an ecosystem?
- A) Providing energy and matter for other organisms.
 - B) Consuming energy and matter in an ecosystem.
 - C) Causing dead plant or animal matter to decompose.
 - D) Providing shelter for other organisms.
 - E) All of the above.
- 13) A spider stalks, kills and then eats an insect. Which terms defines the behavior of the spider?
- A) Herbivore, autotroph
 - B) Producer, heterotroph
 - C) Herbivore, consumer
 - D) Carnivore, consumer
 - E) Autotroph, carnivore

- 14) Which of the following occurs if one of the herbivore animal species becomes extinct in an ecosystem?
- A) Increase in diversity of plant species.
 - B) Decrease in amount of organic matter production within the ecosystem.
 - C) Decrease in diversity of plant species.
 - D) Decrease in food competition among the herbivores.
 - E) Increase in diversity of carnivore species.
- 15) When petroleum is burned, carbon dioxide is released to the air. What causes carbon to get into the petroleum in the first place?
- A) Refineries
 - B) Plant respiration
 - C) Decomposing planktons
 - D) Photosynthesis in plants
 - E) Meteors
- 16) Energy forms can be ...
- A) Chemical
 - B) Thermal
 - C) Electrical
 - D) Radiant
 - E) All of the above
- 17) Energy transformations that involve chemical changes also produce ...
- A) Electricity
 - B) Friction
 - C) Radiation
 - D) Heat
 - E) Sound
- 18) What kind of energy do you take in when you eat food?
- A) Thermal
 - B) Electrical
 - C) Chemical
 - D) Nuclear
 - E) Sound

- 19) Coal is used in thermal power plants to produce energy. The produced energy is brought to the consumers through the electrical transmission and distribution networks. What percentage of the total energy produced reaches the consumers?
- A) 100%
 - B) 90%
 - C) 30%
 - D) 5%
 - E) 1%
- 20) Transformers are electrical devices used to change the voltage from one level to another and use the principle of
- A) Electromagnetic induction
 - B) Friction
 - C) Electrolysis
 - D) Super conductivity
 - E) Electroluminescence
- 21) Which one of following does NOT cause pollution?
- A) Smoking a cigarette outside of a building
 - B) Throwing plastic bottles into a forest
 - C) Pouring excess soft drinks into a lake
 - D) Fallen leaves from a tree
 - E) Noise created by a wind energy power plants
- 22) What are some ways that we can keep away from polluting?
- A) Using things produced by chemicals that are non-harmful to the environment
 - B) Using bicycles instead of cars for travelling
 - C) Reusing product packages as flower pots
 - D) Recycling water bottles
 - E) All answers are correct.
- 23) Which one of the air pollutants below can damage lungs?
- A) Ozone
 - B) Carbondioxide
 - C) Nitrogen
 - D) Carbon Monoxide
 - E) All answers are correct

- 24) Which is an example of water pollution?
- A) sugar factory wastewater poured into a river without proper treatment
 - B) cattles drinking and washing inside a lake
 - C) creating illegal dumping sites near a river
 - D) an oil spill from a large ship
 - E) all answers are correct
- 25) Which of the following is an example of solid waste?
- A) things in a trash can
 - B) broken furniture that has been thrown away
 - C) an old bicycle
 - D) used plastic bottles
 - E) All answers are correct.
- 26) Which of the following is not a renewable energy resource?
- A) Wind
 - B) Natural Gas
 - C) Solar
 - D) Biomass
 - E) Wave
- 27) Which of the following best describes the renewable energy?
- A) Energy from fossil fuels
 - B) Energy that is generated by burning up something
 - C) An energy source that is not used up
 - D) All of the above
 - E) None of the above
- 28) Why is developing renewable energy important to life on Earth?
- A) Other energy sources will be used up
 - B) Renewable energy can last forever
 - C) Renewable energy produces less pollution
 - D) All of the above
 - E) None of the above

- 29) What type of renewable energy comes from building dams on rivers?
- A) Wind power
 - B) Solar power
 - C) Wave power
 - D) Hydropower
 - E) Geothermal energy
- 30) What type of renewable energy comes from tapping heat generated inside the Earth?
- A) Geothermal energy
 - B) Wave power
 - C) Wind power
 - D) Solar power
 - E) Nuclear power
- 31) What is the least preferable waste management option?
- A) Recycle
 - B) Reuse
 - C) Reduce
 - D) Burning
 - E) Landfilling
- 32) What is the most preferable waste management option?
- A) Recycle
 - B) Reuse
 - C) Reduce
 - D) Burning
 - E) Landfilling
- 33) What does “e-waste” stands for?
- A) industrial waste
 - B) electronical waste
 - C) spam e-mail
 - D) hazardous chemical waste
 - E) none of the above
- 34) Which one of the following is generates municipal solid waste?

- A) Paper production facility with 50 workers
 - B) Brewery industry with 100 workers
 - C) University campus
 - D) Hospital having 1000 bed capacity
 - E) All of the above
- 35) Which is NOT an example of how the “3R rule” can be adopted by a city?
- A) Disposing plastic bottles in a landfill
 - B) Composting organic waste
 - C) Recovering heat from combustible waste
 - D) Offering collection of recyclables from apartment buildings once a week
 - E) All of the above

GREEN ENERGY SURVEY ANSWER KEY

- 1- D
- 2- B
- 3- C
- 4- A
- 5- B
- 6- D
- 7- D
- 8- A
- 9- A
- 10- D
- 11- B
- 12- E
- 13- D
- 14- D
- 15- C
- 16- E
- 17- D
- 18- C
- 19- C
- 20- A
- 21- D
- 22- E
- 23- A
- 24- E
- 25- E
- 26- B
- 27- C
- 28- D
- 29- D
- 30- A
- 31- E
- 32- C
- 33- B
- 34- E
- 35- C

GREEN4U GAMINGS' MEASUREMENT SHEET

		A	B	C	D	E
Date (DD/MM/YYYY) :	■ 1	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Name & Surname :	■ 2	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Age :	■ 3	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Grade :	■ 4	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
City & Country :	■ 5	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Signature :	■ 6	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 7	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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		■ 14	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
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		■ 18	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 19	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 20	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
To be filled by the instructor in:		■ 21	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Overall Score :	■ 22	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Remarks :	■ 23	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 24	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 25	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 26	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Name & Surname :	■ 27	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 28	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Signature :	■ 29	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 30	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 31	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 32	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 33	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 34	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
		■ 35	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

Furthermore

- Let students create their own crazy ideas on green energy topics: Observe the development in thinking on green energy,
- Ask the students, individual or small groups, draw a poster on green energy topics. Let them present their work. Observe the tendency of topics included in the posters.

Postface

Young people in different countries are in demand of having more knowledge and awareness on green energy subjects, although they are under different educational programs. We have estimated that the young people, aged 13 to 25 years old, pay high attention to digital platforms. The quality of graphics is of interest. They are good candidates to be educated through digital platforms. Unfortunately serious games are seemd to be often boring stuff. The pedogogs must carefully work so that educational material is hidden behind attractive games.

On the other hand young people are open to study the topics of green energy. Through some seminars or tools of our project, young people can be easily attracted to green energy sites.

We have estimated that the progress in knowledge on green energy by applying the tools of our project is more then 70%. We believe that our outputs can be used in especially secondary and high schools, public education centers and in workshops related to green energy topics.

Data Privacy, Gaming and Green For Youth Games

The Law on the Protection of Personal Data No. 6698 was published in the Official Gazette on 7 April 2016 and entered into force to provide the protection of personal data and the fundamental rights related with privacy and freedom stated in the Constitution. Data Protection Law provides that personal data which is obtained within the framework of the general principles specified in the Law can only be transferred with the explicit consent of the data subject.

The data privacy regulations impact companies and projects in the gaming space. Bad people, the creators or the distributors of the games, doing sneaky things to get peoples data cause the increase in data privacy regulations, especially the use of children's data has become an increasingly big deal for games in the industry.

Since different countries have different regulations such as KVKK of Turkey and GDPR of Europe, in multinational projects there may be a "lack of clarity" around implementations. Because of this, partners of the Green for Youth Project chose not to collect opinions and evaluations from inside the games. Instead, pilot game playing and focus groups took place.

Annex

3rd International Scientific Conference on Philosophy of Mind and Cognitive Modelling in Education

The first results of the project were presented in the international conference "3rd International Scientific Conference on Philosophy of Mind and Cognitive Modelling in Education" 07-08.05.2018, Maribor, Slovenia.

**3rd International Scientific Conference on Philosophy
of Mind and Cognitive Modelling in Education**

Conference Programme

Monday, 07. 05. 2018

8.00 9.00 Registration

9.00 9.20 *Opening ceremony speakers*

dr. Mitja Slavinec, Dean of Faculty for Natural Science and
Mathematics

dr. Zdenka Petermanec, Director of UKM

ddr. Boris Aberšek, Conference chair

***Session 1 (Chairman: Boris Aberšek)
formal language is English***

9.20	9.40	Pre-service teacher health literacy: understanding, development, significance aspects <i>Vincentas Lamanauskas</i>
9.40	10.00	Philosophy of artificial intelligence <i>Janez Bregant</i>
10.00	10.20	ICT in chemistry didactics <i>Martin Bilek</i>
10.20	10.40	Comparing the views of pupils and teachers on using of music in teaching foreign languages <i>Petra Besedova</i>
10.40	11.00	Intelligent serious games for learning in informal learning environment <i>Metka Kordigel Aberšek, Kosta Dolenc, Cecilia Sik-Lanyi, Shervin Shirmohammadi, Karel Van Isacker, Petya Grudeva, Veronika Szucs, Tibor Guzsvinecz</i>

11.00 11.15 Coffee Break

**Session 2 (Chairman: Vincentas Lamanauskas)
formal language is English**

- 11.15 11.35 Design of measuring and evaluating the emotional state for effective education using the internet of things
Zoltán Balogh, Jan Francisti, Milan Turčáni,
- 11.35 11.55 Green Energy Skills for Youth
Boris Aberšek, Metka Kordigel Aberšek, Anže Boh, Şahin Uyaver, Neşe Aral, Alper Özpınar, Şaha Özpınar, Igor Krobkov; Ivan Gartsev, Peter Lubej
- 11.55 12.15 Lower secondary stem teachers shortage in Slovenia is following European trends
Kosta Dolenc, Mateja Ploj Virtič, Boris Aberšek
- 12.15 12.35 Permanent teachers' training as the cornerstone of the successful implementation of innovative learning environments
Maja Vičič Krabonja, Magdalena Šverc, Andrej Flogie
- 12.55 13.15 VR and web accessibility
Cecilia Sik Lanyi

13.15 14.30 Lunch Break (by your own arrangement)

**Session 3 (Chairman: Metka Kordigel Aberšek)
formal language is Slovenian**

- 14.30 14.50 Le Guin's The Dispossessed: A Case Study of Thought Experiments in Fiction
Bojan Borstner, Tadej Todorovič
- 14.50 15.10 Creating of a dictionary as a teaching method in learning German
Golob-Koman Alenka
- 15.10 15.30 Uporaba moderne tehnologije pri pouku – spodbujanje kreativnosti ali digitalne demence
Bauman Nataša

15.30 15.45 Coffee Break

Session 4 (Chairman: Kosta Dolenc)
formal language is Slovenian

15.45	16.05	Kviz Kahoot! - dobra motivacija ali zgolj igra <i>Bremec Darja</i>
16.05	16.25	Kako preseči pasivnost dijakov pri pouku strokovno teoretičnih predmetov <i>Dolenšek Gabrijela</i>
16.25	16.45	Uporaba programa sketchup pri pouku tehnike in tehnologije v osnovni šoli <i>Košak Igor</i>
16.45	17.05	Pristopi k razvoju in izdelavi pripomočkov za varno in učinkovito rabo mobilnih naprav v inovativnem učnem okolju <i>Volarič Boris</i>

17.05 17.20 Coffee Break

Session 5 (Chairman: Mateja Ploj Vrtič)
formal language is Slovenian

17.20	17.40	Aktivno učenje tujega jezika preko strokovnih besedil <i>Grum Špela</i>
17.40	18.00	So dijaki zasvojeni s pametnimi telefoni? <i>Hrastnik Gregor</i>
18.00	18.20	Aplikacije, ki mi lajšajo delo pri pouku <i>Škrabl Nastja</i>
18.20	18.40	Primer uporabe informacijsko komunikacijske tehnologije pri pouku športne vzgoje <i>Jablanov Goran</i>
18.40	19.00	Poučevanje glasbe z ustvarjanjem in s pomočjo informacijsko-komunikacijske tehnologije (IKT) <i>Vučič Jasmina</i>
19.00		End of sessions

Tuesday, 08. 05. 2018 (formal language is Slovenian)

**Session 6 (Chairman: Magdalena Šverc)
Glazerjeva dvorana**

9.00	9.20	Razvijanje digitalnih kompetenc na primeru globalnega segrevanja pri geografiji v srednji šoli <i>Kancler Jovita</i>
9.20	9.40	Nekatera IKT orodja za obrnjeno učenje <i>Koderman Ivo</i>
9.40	10.00	Vpliv inkluzije na kognitiven razvoj učencev pri pouku športa <i>Krevh Alojz</i>
10.00	10.20	Tipkanje namesto rokopisa – vpliv programske opreme na pisanje in kakovost literarnega eseja v gimnaziji <i>Mandeljc Milan</i>

10.20 10.35 Coffee Break

**Session 7 (Chairman: Bogomir Marčinkovič)
Učilnica Brede Filo**

9.00	9.20	IKT kot pomembna komponenta razvijanja veščin pri pouku geografije v osnovni šoli <i>Matkovič Matej</i>
9.20	9.40	Kako oblikovati napredna učna okolja, ki bodo dijakom v multietničnih oddelkih omogočala pozitivne učne izkušnje – Študija primera <i>Meh Peer Nataša</i>
9.40	10.00	Smart phone in the parliament <i>Nemec Andrej</i>
10.00	10.20	Sodelovanje-komunikacija že na razredni stopnji? Zakaj pa ne! Formativno spremljanje in vrednotenje napredka učečih se <i>Novak Lidija</i>

10.20 10.35 Coffee Break

Session 8 (Chairman: Terezija Zamuda)
Glazerjeva dvorana

10.35	10.55	Uporaba telefonov pri pouku – učenci ali učitelj? <i>Pikelj Grobelnik Klavdija</i>
10.55	11.15	Predstavitev malo drugače <i>Pokeržnik Alenka</i>
11.15	11.35	The added value of ict in efl lessons for 13-year-olds <i>Pucko Teo</i>
11.35	11.55	Upravičenost izgradnje samooskrbne mikro sončne elektrarne <i>Čebren Robert</i>
11.55	12.15	Naj se reši, kdor se more <i>Kermc Nataša</i>

12.15 13.30 Lunch Break (by your own arrangement)

Session 9 (Chairman: Robert Gajšek)
Učilnica Brede Filo

10.35	10.55	Formative monitoring by the modul the transformation of non-metallic materials <i>Stropnik Klavdija</i>
10.55	11.15	Uporaba webinarjev pri pouku <i>Žigert Adela</i>
11.15	11.35	Uporaba aplikacij za razvoj socialnih veščin pri učencu z motnjo avtističnega spektra <i>Žibert Katja</i>
11.35	11.55	Umetniško raziskovanje <i>Gajšek Katja</i>
11.55	12.15	Odločitveni model kot ustvarjalni izziv <i>Habinc Tea</i>

12.15 13.30 Lunch Break (by your own arrangement)

Session 10 (Chairman: Maja Vičič Krabonja)

13.30	13.50	Spremljanje razumevanja in doživljanja umetnostnega besedila za domače branje z raznolikimi ustvarjalnimi dejavnostmi <i>Vanja Kolar Ivačič</i>
13.50	14.10	Ne, nisem premajhen. S strategijo problemskega pouka do doseganja zastavljenih ciljev tudi pri najmlajših <i>Leskovar Janja</i>
14.10	14.30	Razvijanje digitalnih kompetenc pri pouku tujih jezikov v OŠ <i>Meglič Ana, Perović Ana</i>
14.30	14.50	Learner-centred education in design and technology classes <i>Anja Jug, Mateja Ploj Vrtič</i>
14.50	15.10	Potential uses of the mobile phone as a learning tool in the educational proces <i>Cvek Mihaela, Pšunder Mateja</i>

15.10

Closing ceremony

Session 11 (Poster Session)

Intelligent Serious Games for Social and Cognitive Competence
*Shervin Shirmohammadi (Department of Computer Science and Engineering, Istanbul Sehir University, Istanbul, **Turkey**)*

Intelligent Serious Games for Social and Cognitive Competence
*Karel Van Isacker (PHOENIXKM BVBA, Kortemark, **Belgium**)*

Intelligent Serious Games for Social and Cognitive Competence
*Petya Grudeva (ZGURA-M Ltd., Plovdiv, **Bulgaria**)*

Intelligent Serious Games for Social and Cognitive Competence
*Veronika Szucs (Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Systems, University of Pannonia, Veszprem, **Hungary**)*

Intelligent Serious Games for Social and Cognitive Competence
*Tibor Guzsvinecz (Department of Electrical Engineering and Information Systems, University of Pannonia, Veszprem, **Hungary**)*

Green Energy Skills for Youth
*Şahin Uyaver (Turkish-German University, **Turkey**)*

Green Energy Skills for Youth
*Neşe Aral (Turkish-German University, **Turkey**)*

Green Energy Skills for Youth
*Alper Özpınar (Istanbul Ticaret University, **Turkey**)*

Green Energy Skills for Youth
*Şaha Özpınar (Uskudar University, **Turkey**)*

Green Energy Skills for Youth
*Igor Krobkov (ZentralWeb GmbH, **Germany**)*

Green Energy Skills for Youth
*Ivan Gartsev (ZentralWeb GmbH, **Germany**)*

Green Energy Skills for Youth

Boris Aberšek¹, Metka Kordigel Aberšek¹, Anže Boh¹, Şahin Uyaver², Neşe Aral², Alper Özptınar³; Şaha Özptınar⁴, Igor Krobkov⁵; Ivan Gartsev⁵, Peter Lubej⁶

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Abstract

In relation to young people green skills cover a broad range of topics and initiatives that are concrete and practically-oriented. When talking with young people about green skills teachers and trainers have to start from inflicting some habits of green lifestyle and then proceed to issues like green economy, green jobs and green entrepreneurship. Green skills are not only about some sophisticated and high-profile skills related to the use of new technologies, but also about skills for green society, e.g. life skills, critical thinking, awareness, problem solving. The main objective of the research in frame of the project “Green energy skills for youth” which is an Erasmus+ Strategic Partnership – is to increase awareness and competences of youth for green energies so that they will get skills on climate change, energy production, management of waste, water supply, flood management, biodiversity, etc.

Key words: Green energy, renewable energy, ecological footprint, ecological awareness

Introduction

Environmental challenges raise serious concerns for the welfare of current and future generations. Responses should be driven by independent but commonly reinforcing policies for environment, energy, transportation, employment, and training. In recent years, the effects of global warming have been witnessed over the world. Studies point to human action, like pollution and deforestation, as key reasons for global warming and adverse climate changes. There is an urgent need for all of us, individually and collectively, to become more aware of our environmental responsibilities (Cameron, Stuart, 2012).

In order to understand green skills and their significance today, we need to grasp the concepts of green economy, green jobs and green entrepreneurship which all require a wide range of green skills, depending on the sector in question (Aberšek, 2017). Green economy leads to human well-being and at the same time reduces threats or risks for the environment. It strives for zero carbon emissions, smaller ecological footprint and nourishes natural capital (the world's stock of natural resources which creates a long term supply of goods or services). Green energy mostly connected with renewable energy can be produced from a wide variety of sources including wind, solar, hydro, tidal, geothermal, and biomass. By using more renewables to meet its energy needs, the EU lowers its dependence on imported fossil fuels and makes its energy production more sustainable. The renewable energy industry also drives technological innovation and employment across Europe. Renewables will continue to play a key role in helping the EU meet its energy needs beyond 2020. EU countries have already agreed on a new renewable energy target of at least 27% of final energy consumption in the

EU as a whole by 2030. This target is part of the EU's energy and climate goals for 2030 (GWEC, 2015, OECD, 2011).

When talking with young people about green skills youth workers and trainers have to start from instilling some habits of green lifestyle and then proceed to issues like green economy, green jobs and green entrepreneurship. Thus, the main idea behind green skills mobile game developed was to promote nature responsible behaviour by providing interesting and useful information in an attractive way. By playing the game, the user gets information for recycling of different materials. Other similar games can be developed focusing on similar green issues – e.g. energy-saving methods. Those can provoke interest and understanding of the pollution problems, limitation of natural resources etc.

Research and research methodology

The main idea behind green skills mobile game developed in the project "Green energy skills for youth" was to promote nature responsible behaviour by providing interesting and useful information in an attractive way. By playing the game, the user would get information and awareness of necessity for recycling of different materials. The research in the project "Green energy skills for youth" is targeting following groups, willing to introduce the mobile games training approaches in the youth work:

- youth workers in youth organizations
- youth trainers involved in out-of-school youth activities
- leaders of youth organizations
- young people interested in eco/green skills who will be the final users of the mobile games, developed in the frame of the project.

There will be 2 different methodologies to collect data from target groups and stakeholders. Those are:

- Survey by questionnaire
- Face to face meetings and interviews, as required.

Main Activities and research methods that will be organised and elaborated:

- Design of the questionnaire in Turkish, German and Slovenian and implement of the survey
- Survey and data collecting
- Qualitative and quantitative analysis of findings as comparative report
- Examine results of need analysis survey
- Develop learning content through a curriculum
- Prepare educational content including transposing of elements for broad user groups
- Analyze the results to produce the final full games design document for each scenario
- Develop models and characters (graphics, avatars, objects etc.) identified in the games design document for each learning scenario
- Implement game playing modes for each scenario
- Produce manual to describe hardware/software requirements, usage scenarios, and instructional approach
- Develop usability evaluation plan and materials
- Set up case studies to pilot materials
- Develop evaluation methodology

- Complete case studies and usability evaluation report

Discussion and conclusion

Environmental challenges raise serious concerns for the welfare of current and future generations. In recent years, the effects of global warming have been witnessed over the world. Studies point to human action, like pollution and deforestation, as key reasons for global warming and adverse climate changes. There is an urgent need for all of us, individually and collectively, to become more aware of our environmental responsibilities.

“Green energy skills for youth” proposal will help to improve the quality, attractiveness and accessibility of the opportunities for lifelong learning available by developing interactive intelligent mobile games and stimulations by user generated scenarios for acquiring transversal competencies of youth. The idea "GREEN4U" addresses to improve the green skills, awareness and competences on education enhancing creativity and innovation by using serious games and simulations as pedagogy is definitely creative, attractive and efficient learning.

Project consortium represents a multidisciplinary team for achieving the aims and objectives of this proposal. Each partner comes with unique expertise and experience either in the field of energy systems, environmental engineering, creativity skills, digital competencies, interactive technologies and gaming, policy makers in school or education etc. Project partners are universities, NGOs and mobile multimedia programming and development companies from Turkey, Germany and Slovenia.

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References

Aberšek, B. (2017). Evolution of competences for new era or education 4.0. V: MICHEK, Stanislav (ur.). Vliv technologií v oblasti vzdělávání a v pedagogickém výzkumu : sborník abstraktů z XXV. konference České asociace pedagogického výzkumu konané ve dnech 13.-14. září 2017 v Hradci Králové, XXV. konference České asociace pedagogického výzkumu, 13.-14. Hradec Králové: Gaudeamus.

GWEC (2015). *Global wind report*. Brussel: Global wind energy council

OECD (2011). *Toward green growth. A summary for policy makers*. Paris: OECD

Cameron, A., & Stuart, C. (2012). *A guidebook to the Green Economy*. UN Division for Sustainable Development (UNDESA)

International Conference on Sustainable Energy and Energy Calculations

The results of the project were presented by two papers in the international conference "International Conference on Sustainable Energy and Energy Calculations", 12-14 April 2019, Koycegiz, Mugla, Turkey.

ICSEEC: SUSTAINABLE ENERGY AND ENERGY CALCULATIONS

**Abstracts of International Conference on Sustainable
Energy and Energy Calculations**

 GREEN4YOUTH PROJECT

12– 14 April 2019, Koycegiz, Mugla, Turkey

Organized by

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TÜRKISCH-DEUTSCHE UNIVERSITÄT

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Human Awareness and Ecological Footprint

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In the process of education when we mostly point out importance of getting knowledge, to developing cognitive competences, the question arises of what happens with the students' social skills and their social competences, and whether we can increase social competences gradually, step by step? Human beings are definitely social beings. From our own research, as well as from the research conducted by many other researchers it is obvious that with intensive individualization and differentiation of the teaching/learning process (one-on-one tutoring), a drastic decrease in social skills and social awareness, which is crucial in the area of ecology.

What can / must we do? As we have already mentioned, the recurrent theme of this research will be the "ecological footprint". We must develop awareness in every individual; we must "change" or establish the specific way of thinking (creative, critical, and conscious thinking); and it is very important to begin this process with students of the youngest possible age. In the case of the ecological footprint problem, competences must be developed step by step, which enable us to deal with the day-to-day needs of others, and which help raise the awareness that we have only one earth – a complex puzzle, for which everyone is responsible, and to which everyone can contribute their small (but important) piece.

The analysis of the results of project GREEN4U clearly points to the effectiveness of the proposed research- and problem-based strategies of learning (supported by collaborative teaching/learning) for developing social competences. Nonetheless, a more detailed research with a larger sample of students would have to be conducted in order to receive even more relevant results. The development of historical memory in humans is a gradual process happening over a long period of time. Little by little, lesson by lesson, it is going to alter our own awareness by constructing and adding new elements on the level of intuitive thinking. Such research work will be crucial for developing a complete, integrated, well-rounded personality of a student; for creating positive interpersonal relationships; and for constructing a tolerant society of the future.

New Generations Knowledge and Attitudes about Energy Usage of the World: A Research on Middle and High School Students

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Energy usage of the world is a multi-faceted issue with many macro and micro shareholders. Most of these shareholders has a consensus about harmful effects of energy usage on environment. For this reason, energy efficiency and green energy related issues are gaining importance in today's world. Governments, for-profit/non-profit organizations and also individuals are concerning about the energy usage of modern human. Concerned shareholders are trying to lower the energy usage by means of energy efficiency and/or green energy resources. These efforts are creating some significant results. But these results are not sufficient without a massive change on energy usage habits of people. Changing people's energy usage habits by changing their attitudes, may be an important component of lowering energy usage of world. Thus, rising new generations with a proper knowledge and positive attitude towards energy usage is an important facet of multifaceted energy usage issue. For this reason, this study was conducted with an exploratory spirit for understanding new generations knowledge about energy issues and their attitudes towards energy usage. In order to reach this aim, a survey has been conducted to 1190 students from Turkey. The relation between their knowledge about energy issues, their attitudes towards energy and demographic factors have been studied by this survey results. On last part of the study implications for educational staff and further research directions for researchers have been suggested.